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**Assessing the Impact of Technological Innovation, Natural Gas Rents and
Macroeconomic Factors on the Development of Renewable Energy**

Bsc (Hons) Economics

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Abstract

Since the signing of the Paris Agreement in 2015, countries around the world have been working tirelessly to reduce greenhouse gas emissions in order to address climate change. However, the international community needs to significantly increase investment into renewable energy as environmental concerns continue to grow. The aim of this study is to determine the nature of any relationship between renewable energy investment, innovation, natural gas rents, GDP and the interest rate, using time series analysis. Throughout this investigation, I will focus on three countries with varying relationships with the renewable sector. Following estimation using a VAR model, the results provide evidence of a strong relationship between renewable energy investment and macroeconomic factors in the USA, in contrast to the UK, which reveals no such relationship. These findings reflect the fact that the UK renewable energy market is heavily subsidised by government policy, making it less susceptible to economic factors. Conversely, renewable energy investment in Norway reveals a strong relationship with innovation and natural gas rents due to harnessing energy-related technologies and natural gas revenues. The findings suggest that in order to achieve ambitious climate targets, certain countries should prioritise investment in renewable energy technologies and implement policies that explicitly address the negative consequences of natural gas resources.

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1. Introduction

Since the signing of the Paris Agreement in 2015, countries around the world have been working tirelessly to reduce greenhouse gas emissions in order to address climate change. This has further inspired a number of countries to make commitments to achieve net zero emissions in the coming decades. The transition to climate neutrality has enormous environmental benefits in terms of reducing the adverse effects of production and consumption. However, to reach net zero emissions by 2050, the international community must more than triple annual clean energy investment to around \$4 trillion by 2030 (IEA, 2021). Moreover, as the world continues to grapple with the impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic, it is critical that the resulting wave of investment is aligned with the net zero pathway, but it is unclear what will facilitate this investment.

Renewable energy sources are widely recognised as essential in the fight against climate change. Hence, governments around the world have sought to expand the production of renewable energy to target emissions. Globally, the renewable energy sector has achieved significant overall growth, especially in the last decade, with hydropower being by far the largest modern renewable source, as illustrated by figure 1.

Fig. 1. Renewable energy generation

Source: Our World in Data

The introduction of subsidies and taxation on non-renewable sources has motivated this rise in renewable generation, highlighting the dominant role government intervention plays in the market for renewable energy. However, as noted by Shah *et*

al. (2018), government intervention in this market is declining, due to the increasing competitiveness of innovation in renewable energy technologies.

The main contribution of this paper relates to whether technology progress and natural gas rents significantly affect renewable energy investment. In addition, this paper considers the impact of macroeconomic factors such as real GDP and real interest rates whilst analysing the influence of government policy on renewable energy markets. Furthermore, this is the first-time historical decompositions have been used in the study of renewable energy, enabling a review of its interactions with key variables over time.

Technological innovation, which provides the technical infrastructure for renewable energy, is a significant factor contributing to the reduction of environmental deterioration (Khan *et al.*, 2022). The advancement of technology is essential for the transition to modern, low-carbon energy systems that ensure the efficient use of renewable energy sources to meet rising energy demand. Furthermore, technology integration with renewables is widely accepted as critical in order to achieve sustainable economic growth (Wang, Xiao and Bai, 2022).

Natural gas rents (defined as the difference between the value of natural gas production at regional prices and total costs of production) in recent years have been characterised by extreme volatility, as Russian supply curbs exacerbated a squeeze on the European gas market, pushing prices to a 13-year high (Sheppard *et al.*, 2021). However, its direct impact on renewable energy is massively overlooked within the literature. Throughout this study I offer two conflicting arguments in relation to the potential impact of natural gas rents on renewable energy deployment.

Consequently, this paper pursues several objectives which aims to fill a gap in the literature on the development of future renewable energy resources. First, I present an empirical model which captures the contrasting characteristics of three distinct renewable energy markets in a time series framework. Secondly, I will investigate the interaction between renewable energy and its related variables using the Granger causality test, generalised impulse response functions, variance forecast error and historical decomposition. Furthermore, I implement natural resource rents into the

model to indicate that the results are robust. The overarching objective of this study is to help advance energy policy by casting light on what impact innovation, natural gas rents and macroeconomic factors have on renewable energy investment. I decided to investigate the relationship between renewable energy investment and its related variables on a country-by-country basis, due to the inherent heterogeneities within countries in terms of technological development, natural resources and renewable energy policies. Specifically, I have used annual time series data for the USA, UK and Norway from 1980 to 2020.

The following section reviews theoretical considerations and previous studies. Subsequently, I present an analysis regarding the energy sector in the USA, UK and Norway before outlining the methodology and data description. I then provide the empirical findings before offering conclusive remarks.

2. Literature Review

The purpose of this literature review is to explore whether innovation, natural gas rents and macroeconomic factors drive or restrain renewable development and deployment. A recurring theme in this area of research is that renewable energy investment has not been able to compete historically with traditional fossil fuels in terms of cost and certainty of future returns, as noted by Shah *et al.* (2018). As a consequence, most of the literature related to renewable energy has focused on how government policy can be used to promote renewable investment. Polzin *et al.* (2015) investigated the effectiveness of such public policy measures and concluded that technology-specific policies would be most impactful on investments in renewable energy.

2.1. Technology and Innovation

Firstly, technological advancement achieved through research and development (R&D) is deemed essential to raise renewable energy investment. Gielen *et al.* (2019) have highlighted the importance of technologies linked to renewable energy in providing a framework that defines the future of energy security. Innovation is essential in this context because more advanced technologies are intrinsically linked to lower renewable energy generation costs.

Furthermore, enhanced technologies play a crucial role in improving the efficiency of energy systems, thereby facilitating a greater deployment and utilisation of renewable energy (Sawin *et al.*, 2017). As a result, technological innovation is recognised as one of the most effective means of developing renewable energy in the context of promoting sustainable development.

An analysis by Alam and Murad (2020) reveals that the augmentation of technological progress in OECD countries significantly influences renewable energy. They further argued that technological progress in any nation is paramount if renewable energy is to be promoted. Given that the majority of OECD countries are wealthy, technologically advanced, and heavily engaged in international trade, their access to improved technological resources for generating renewable energy is easier than that of other nations.

Bamati and Raoofi (2020) examined the determinants of renewable energy for two panels of developed and developing countries. Using GLS (Generalized Least Square) panel data estimation method, the results reveal that renewable energy production is significantly determined by high technology export in developed countries, but not in developing countries. The authors attribute this primarily to the fact that high technology export is not considerable in developing countries.

Khan *et al.*, (2022) use a vector autoregression (VAR) model to examine the causality between technology innovations and renewable energy in Germany. Their findings show that technology innovation drives renewable energy positively and negatively across multiple sub-samples. Further, Khan *et al.*, (2021) estimated the short and long-term impact of technological innovations on renewable energy consumption in selected BRI countries. The study's results showed that innovations have a negative relationship with renewable energy. In contrast, financial development is observed as a significant determinant of renewable energy. Hence, the authors noted more funds are required to be transferred to R&D to support renewable energy investment plans. Nevertheless, the results of the Granger non-causality test indicated bidirectional causality between technological innovations and renewable energy which contradicts

the study by Khattak *et al.* (2020), who concluded unidirectional causality from renewable energy to innovations for BRICS countries.

Another study by Irandoust (2016) examines the relationship between renewable energy consumption and technological innovation in the four Nordic countries (Denmark, Finland, Norway and Sweden) by constructing a VAR model. The Granger non-causality test indicated unidirectional causality from technological innovation to renewable energy in all countries.

Tang and Tan (2013), study the causal relationship between CO₂ emissions, growth, and clean energy in Malaysia over the period 1970–2009. The results based on the ARDL approach show that technological innovation is significant in mitigating the usage of fossil fuels. Fei *et al.* (2014) also explore this causal relationship in New Zealand and Norway over the period 1971–2010. According to their findings, technological innovation plays an important role in the clean energy-growth nexus.

Matallah *et al.* (2023) investigated the interactions between oil rents, innovation and renewable energy generation in 8 oil-rich MENA countries over the period 1996-2020. The results emphasise the importance of innovation in promoting renewable energy in MENA oil exporting countries.

Khezri *et al.* (2021) investigate the effects of renewable energy determinants on various renewable energy resources based on data from 31 mainly Asia-Pacific countries observed from 2000 to 2018. The study focused primarily on the role of R&D, which discovered that R&D enhancements reduce the impact of market expansion on hydropower; however, such effects are incremental for alternative renewable energy resources.

Another investigation by Xie *et al.* (2020) determined whether improving existing technologies allow for an increase in renewable energy consumption. Their research revealed that the creation of new technologies through innovative endeavours is essential for expanding the use of renewable energy. Conversely, existing technologies fail to have a significant impact.

2.2. Natural Gas Rents

Natural gas rents are viewed as the net revenues after subtracting the cost of extraction. The impact of natural gas rents on the deployment of renewable energy is largely unexplored; however, given the importance of natural gas as component of national production in some countries, it is crucial to investigate.

The gross domestic product (GDP) of natural gas-rich nations is typically supported by vast infrastructures based on natural gas resources. When natural gas rents are high, natural gas-rich developed nations are expected to invest in renewable energy to diversify their energy supply. Nonetheless, some nations strengthen their commitment to traditional energy sources by increasing investment in existing fossil-based infrastructure, which hinders the capacity for renewable energy (Bamati and Raoofi, 2020). This highlights the importance of good governance in order to envision real progress in the transition to renewable energy. Khan, Su and Zhu (2022) used the quantile-on-quantile methodology to examine the impact of the quantiles of economic policy uncertainty (EPU) on the quantiles of renewable energy in the G7 countries. It shows that conducive government policies are vital for renewable energy development in these countries.

Although there is a shortage of studies linking investment into renewable energy to natural gas rents, Korkmaz (2022) analyses the role of oil, gas and coal rents on the production and consumption of renewable energy for the USA and China. In the USA, the author discovered causal links confirming gas rents and other variables cause renewable energy production and consumption, whereas in China, the variables only reveal a long-term relationship with renewable energy consumption.

Ahmadov and van der Borg (2019) investigate the impact of natural resource rents on renewable energy production in EU nations. Using a mixed-methods research design that combined panel data analysis with an in-depth comparative case study, the paper demonstrates that an overall abundance of natural resources may be conducive while petroleum wealth negatively affects renewable energy production.

An investigation by Wu *et al.* (2022) analysed the nexus of natural resource volatility, carbon emissions, renewable energy resources, and economic performance in the BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa) economies. The study's results asserted that natural gas rents are positively associated with economic performance. In spite of their contribution to economic growth, traditional energy sources such as oil, gas, and coal account for the majority of industrial CO₂ emissions, as demonstrated by empirical evidence. Consequently, policies that consider the transition of the industrial sector from fossil fuels to renewable energy by providing subsidies for renewables adaptation must be developed.

Other studies have investigated the impact of natural gas prices on renewable energy. Wang *et al.*, (2022) explored the opportunities and challenges for renewable energy brought by the skyrocket of natural gas prices in China. The authors quantified the impact of rising natural gas prices on renewable energy based on the R-MILP model. Under the low-carbon tax policy, their findings demonstrated that high natural gas prices are more likely to encourage the development of low-cost non-renewable power generation. To improve the capacity of renewable energy for power generation the authors emphasised the cost reduction benefits of technological upgrading. Further, Sarmiento *et al.*, (2021) examined the impact of natural gas prices on the structure and costs of the power systems in the U.S. and Mexico. Their results asserted that high natural gas prices raise the use of carbon intensive technologies in the short-term and boost renewable investments at the long term.

2.3. GDP

The impact of GDP on renewable energy has been a topic of interest in this field of study for many years. Bamati and Raoofi (2020) argue that any model attempting to explain the production of renewable energy must incorporate GDP as a measure of income.

On one hand, higher GDP may create a policy environment that is conducive to renewable sources, resulting in a positive effect. On the other hand, the costs of replacing infrastructures utilising traditional energy sources, such as fossil fuels, are substantial, thus limiting the emergence of renewable sources.

Alam and Murad (2020) also investigated the short-term and long-term impacts of economic growth on renewable energy. They concluded that economic growth significantly influences renewable energy use over the long-term in OECD countries.

Sadorsky (2009) estimated a panel model of renewable energy consumption for the G7 countries. The study revealed that in the long term, increases in real GDP per capita are found to be major drivers behind per capita renewable energy consumption.

Another study by Menyah and Wolde-Rufael (2010) explored the causal relationship between renewable energy consumption and real GDP for the USA between 1960–2007. Using a modified version of the Granger causality test, their findings are consistent with Sadorsky (2009), discovering that real national income is a significant driver of renewable energy use.

The heterogeneous panel cointegration test conducted by Apergis and Payne (2010) revealed a long-run equilibrium relationship as well as bidirectional causality between renewable energy and economic growth in a panel of OECD countries. These results are in line with Apergis *et al.* (2010) who found a bidirectional causal relationship between renewable energy and economic growth for a group of 19 developed and developing countries. Apergis and Payne (2014) further utilise panel cointegration techniques to estimate the causal dynamics associated with renewable energy consumption per capita for a panel of 11 South American countries. Over the period 1980 to 2010, the study revealed a bidirectional causal relationship between renewable energy consumption per capita and real GDP per capita. The authors argue the presence of bidirectional causality supports the feedback hypothesis according to which renewable energy use and economic growth are interdependent. In addition, they argued that the positive effect of using renewable energy on economic growth bolsters the viability of the renewable energy sector, providing additional support for the claim that renewable energy can serve as an important energy source for these countries.

Nguyen and Kakinaki (2019) analysed how the relationship between renewable energy consumption and output is associated with the development stage by applying a panel cointegration analysis to 107 countries during the period from 1990 to 2013. Their

study found a positive correlation between renewable energy consumption and output in high-income countries, but a negative correlation in low-income countries.

2.4. Interest Rates

The deployment of renewable energy is heavily dependent on interest rates which has a significant impact on the financing of renewable energy projects. As highlighted by Egli *et al.* (2018), renewable energy cost reductions not only stem from technological innovation but also, to a significant extent, arise from improved financing conditions. In this context, facilitating renewable investment through lowering interest rates is essential in order to achieve a cleaner future.

Shah *et al.* (2018) model the relationship between renewable energy investment, oil prices, GDP and the interest rate, using a time series approach. Following estimation using a VAR model, the results of the Granger causality test provide evidence of a strong relationship between GDP, interest rates and renewable energy in the USA and Norway. Furthermore, GDP and interest rates capture a significant amount of the variation in renewable energy in the USA, indicating that investment in renewable energy is sensitive to borrowing costs. The authors proposed that in countries where the renewable energy sector receives little support, such as in the USA, renewable energy investments will be influenced by macroeconomic factors.

Razmi *et al.* (2021) investigated the impact of monetary policy on renewable energy generation in Iran. The study uses the VAR model to examine annual data from 1984 to 2016. The results from the VAR model showed that none of the renewable energies responded significantly to a positive shock to the real interest rate. This finding is consistent with Shah *et al.* (2018), as they find a negligible response of renewable energy to an interest rate shock.

Another study by Schmidt *et al.* (2019) shows that rising interest rates can reverse the trend of decreasing renewable energy costs, particularly in Europe with its historically low interest rates, jeopardizing the sustainable energy transition.

Finally, Sohag *et al.* (2021) explored the role of real interest rates in driving green growth, considering OECD countries. Their investigation reveals that higher real

interest rates act as a hindrance towards the development of green growth in the long run due to their adverse effect on green investment and cost of finance. However, their findings imply that the real interest rate appears to be insignificant for green growth in the sub-sample countries that provide higher subsidies and grants to the various shareholders of renewable energy. This result suggests that grants and subsidies may mitigate the deleterious effect of higher real interest rates.

3. Country Background and Policies

The paper focuses on individual country analysis, as the relationship between renewable energy investment, innovation, natural gas rents and other macroeconomic variables is likely to vary substantially across countries, depending on each country's innovative capacity, reliance on natural gas and renewable energy policies. The countries analysed are the USA, UK and Norway because of their experience in developing clean energy technologies and diverse policy approaches regarding subsidies and taxes for the renewable energy sector. Furthermore, they have a relatively long time series of data as a result of their sustained interest in renewable energy.

3.1. USA

The USA is regarded as one of the most innovative economies in the world due to its development of advanced and emerging technologies. In the energy space, the USA is a global leader in energy-related research, with strong financial support led by the Department of Energy (DOE) and its 17 national labs, which are regarded as world-class energy research and development centres (IEA, 2019a). Moreover, research into modernising the power grid is also becoming a more important focal point as many states pursue ambitious decarbonisation goals for 2030. The USA is also heavily engaged in international collaboration and innovation in clean energy using the results of its world-class R&D (IEA, 2019a).

The USA has been the leading natural gas producer in the world since 2009, when the country surpassed production levels of the Russian Federation. Most of the natural gas produced in the USA is the result of innovations in gas extraction via horizontal

drilling and hydraulic fracturing (IEA, 2019a). Historically, the USA has been a net importer of natural gas until 2017 in which the country became a net exporter propelled by the shale gas revolution. According to BP Statistical Review of World Energy 2021, natural gas production in the USA grew 5.2% between 2009-19 to reach record levels of 930 billion cubic metres (BCM). The USA has benefited from its advanced natural gas infrastructure, which includes a vast network of pipelines and storage facilities, resulting in lower production costs. Moreover, the USA is committed to expanding its investments in natural gas with a view to reducing carbon emissions and exporting incremental supplies, especially to Europe (Deloitte, 2023).

Renewable energy is playing an increasingly important role in the USA, especially in power generation. In 2020, renewables accounted for 21% of electricity generation, after an unprecedented growth of wind and solar across the USA, driven by lower costs and state policies such as renewable portfolio standards, which mandate that a certain percentage of a state's electric power sales come from renewable energy sources (EIA, 2023). The US government has also launched several other renewable energy policies to accelerate the transition to a clean energy economy. For instance, the US Treasury introduced a series of clean energy tax credits, including the Production Tax Credit (PTC) and the Investment Tax Credit (ITC), to secure growth in renewable energy (IEA, 2019a). Grants and loans are also made available from several government agencies to support the continued integration of renewables into the US power system. Such federal incentives are essential for decarbonising the economy and achieving the government's goal of 80% renewable energy production by 2030 (Mai, 2023). Overall, investment has increased proportionally to the increase in renewable production, reaching \$55.5 billion in 2019 (Krämer, 2020).

3.2. UK

The UK is widely regarded as one of the world's most innovative economies, with a long history of scientific and technological advancement. Despite the challenges of Brexit, the UK has remained committed to leading world class R&D to help advance its productive capacity. Furthermore, the UK has made significant strides towards achieving its energy policy goals of decarbonising heat and electrifying transportation, while delivering growth in technology development and innovation (IEA, 2019b). For instance, the UK's Clean Growth Strategy, of 2017 sets out policies and government

funding of £2.5 billion for innovation and low-carbon investment up to 2021 (Clean Growth Strategy, 2018). Moreover, the UK is also increasing its efforts to accelerate the development of innovative technologies, specifically in the offshore wind industry.

Following the expansion of UK natural gas production in the early 1970s, demand soared, reaching a record high of 1,125 TWh in 2004. Since then, demand has seen an overall decline, and in 2020, it was nearly a third less than the 2004 peak, at 809 TWh (UK energy in brief, 2021). The longer-term trends are driven primarily by commodity prices and changes in energy efficiency. Despite production declines, the UK remains one of the three major gas-producing nations within Europe. Furthermore, the domestic production of natural gas in the North Sea has improved in recent times as a result of the government's repeal of the petroleum revenue tax and reduction of the supplementary charge from 32% to 10% (IEA, 2019b). Overall, natural gas continues to play a crucial role in the UK's energy sector, especially in reducing carbon intensity.

The UK has one of the most well-established renewable sectors, which has achieved remarkable growth in recent years. In June 2019, the UK became the first major economy to enshrine 'net-zero' by 2050 in law, accelerating momentum in the renewable sector ever since (Lu *et al.*, 2020). Notably, in 2020, renewables accounted for more than 43% of the UK's total electricity production (National Grid, 2023). This renewable energy is derived from a variety of sources, including wind, solar, hydroelectric, and bioenergy. The UK has introduced a variety of subsidies and taxes on non-renewable energy sources to encourage the production and consumption of renewable energy. For instance, the contracts for difference (CFD) scheme, which acts as the main mechanism for supporting new large-scale renewable energy generation, provides long term contracts to low-carbon electricity generators. The CFDs improve the predictability of the income, and thus reduce the cost of capital for new renewable energy projects (IEA, 2019b). Other support schemes, such as the renewables obligation (RO) and the feed-in tariff (FIT), have contributed to the development of a competitive renewable energy industry, which is critical to the UK's pursuit of clean energy. Overall, investment in renewable energy has increased in tandem with the rise in renewable generation, which is primarily driven by government policy and legislation.

3.3. Norway

Norway is renowned for its innovative culture and long history of technological leadership in hydropower. The Norwegian government has set ambitious goals for the overall national level of R&D in order to lead the world in developing new technologies for decarbonising hard-to-abate sectors. In 2020, Norway allocated by far the largest share of GDP on energy related R&D spending of all IEA countries, at 0.1% (IEA, 2022). In this context, innovation will play an important role in Norway's energy transition, in particular to leverage the existing strengths of its energy sector in new areas, including carbon capture and storage (CCS) and hydrogen. Moreover, the establishment of Innovation Norway has massively supported domestic businesses and promoted value creation, particularly in the energy sector, through the provision of environmental technology grants.

Norway is the seventh-largest natural gas producer in the world, supplying 3% of global gas consumption, thanks to its abundant natural gas reserves (IEA, 2022). Considerable amounts of Norway's natural gas production are exported annually, as domestic consumption is minimal. For instance, Europe receives approximately 98% of Norway's natural gas production (IEA, 2022). Consequently, the gas industry is a significant source of export revenue for the Norwegian state, which finances the world's largest sovereign wealth fund (GPF), protecting the country's long-term economy from volatility in gas revenues. Furthermore, in light of significant resource rents associated with the extraction of gas, the government applies a special tax of 56% on income from petroleum extraction (IEA, 2022). Nonetheless, despite the country's strong ties to natural gas production, Norway's commitment to a clean energy transition and net zero emissions by 2050 threatens the country's future gas exploration.

Norway has the highest renewable energy share of any IEA member country, driven almost entirely because of its extensive hydropower capabilities. Extraordinarily, in 2020, 98% of electricity generation in Norway came from renewable energy sources (IEA, 2022). In contrast to many other countries, the majority of Norway's renewable energy supply has been provided without significant subsidies due to its extensive hydropower resources (Shah *et al.*, 2018). Nevertheless, the Norwegian government has put in place a number of market-oriented policies to help with long-term

decarbonisation. For instance, Norway was one of the first countries to put in place a carbon tax, in 1991, which has played a key role in spurring investment in CCS technologies (IEA, 2022). In addition, Norway and Sweden have had a joint renewable electricity certificate market since 2012, which is set to end in 2035, to support the growth of renewable generation (IEA, 2022). Such policies have supported the increase in renewable energy investment in Norway, reflecting the country's commitment to establishing a low-emission society by 2050.

To summarise, all three countries are heavily investing in R&D technologies, particularly in the energy space. As a result, I expect a significant relationship between renewable energy investment and innovation, especially in Norway, where energy-related R&D spending as a share of GDP is impressive. Furthermore, natural gas is a major industry in all three countries evaluated. However, given the relative importance of gas revenues to the Norwegian economy I anticipate that natural gas rents will have a significant impact on renewable energy investment. Although, Norway may be more resilient to changes in natural gas rents due to the government's pension fund. While the renewable energy sectors of the USA, UK and Norway share some similarities, there are significant differences in terms of policy and renewable energy mix. In the USA, for example, renewable energy policy varies by state and provides relatively little support in contrast to the UK. Norway has several incentives to encourage renewable energy production, however, the level of support provided by these policies is not as significant. Therefore, I would expect renewable energy investment to be more responsive to market factors in the USA and Norway in comparison to the UK.

4. Renewable Energy Model

This paper performs time series analysis to identify potential drivers of renewable energy investment in terms of innovation, natural gas rents, real GDP and real interest rates in three developed countries.

The variables employed in this study are selected on the basis of economic theory and data availability. Based on the findings of previous literature and our discussion about the expected linkages between renewable energy and the macroeconomy, the following

empirical relationship can be used to describe the determinants of renewable energy investment:

(1)

$$REI = f(INO, NGR, RGDP, RIR)$$

Where *REI* represents renewable energy investment which is a function of four potential drivers including innovation (*INO*), natural gas rents (*NGR*), real GDP (*RGDP*), and real interest rates (*RIR*).

Innovation has been introduced into the model, given the importance of technology progress in enhancing the efficiency of renewable energy technologies. Clean energy technology cost reductions are widely regarded as essential in order to achieve a sustainable transition towards a cleaner future. Hence, effective cost reductions as a result of innovation can motivate increased private investment in renewable energy. Furthermore, several studies have concluded that technological development plays an effective role in the energy-growth nexus, namely Irandoust (2016). As highlighted in section 3.3, Norway places a high value on innovation in the energy space and therefore I would expect a closer relationship between renewable energy and technological progress.

The model includes natural gas rents over natural gas prices to provide a more accurate picture of the economic benefits of gas extraction, as natural gas rents account for both the market price of natural gas and the cost of production. Furthermore, the role of natural gas within the renewable energy market is complex, as it can both support and hinder the development of renewable energy. On one hand, countries with significant natural gas reserves can utilise revenues derived from natural gas to invest in alternative sources of energy in order to strengthen energy security. In addition, natural gas can serve as a flexible transition fuel which can help support the integration of renewable energy into the grid. However, higher natural gas rents coupled with inadequate institutional quality and poor governance can lead to a reluctance to invest in renewable energy sources. Furthermore, natural gas may crowd out renewable energy over extended periods. Overall, I would anticipate a stronger relationship between renewable energy and natural gas rents in economies that rely more heavily

on natural gas. Given the dependence of Norway's economy on gas stocks and its share in production worldwide, it can be said that natural gas rents have an enormous impact on renewable energy investment.

In addition, real GDP is a critical factor that can influence renewable energy as highlighted in the literature review and has therefore been included in the model. Firstly, real GDP impacts the government's ability to implement policies that aim to incentivise the development of renewable energy. Moreover, a growing economy can potentially lead to more investment opportunities becoming available for renewable energy projects. Additionally, as highlighted by Alam and Murad (2020), renewable energy is driven by economic growth, particularly within wealthier countries. Therefore, I would expect a positive relationship between real GDP and renewable energy investment.

Finally, the real interest rate is also included in the model to account for the monetary side of the economy. The real interest rate can have a significant impact on renewable energy specifically through the cost of capital which is a key determinant of private sector investment. Furthermore, several studies examined in the literature review confirm that higher real interest rates hinder renewable energy development, specifically Sohag *et al.* (2021). Hence, I would expect a relationship between renewable energy investment and real interest rates, particularly within more market orientated economies.

4.1. Methodology

To evaluate the relationship between renewable energy investment, innovation, natural gas rents and macroeconomic factors, the study employs an unrestricted VAR model, as previously used within the literature. The decision to apply an unrestricted VAR over a Structural VAR is because this investigation aims to identify the dynamics of renewable energy investment without imposing any prior restrictions. Furthermore, this area of literature has specified the significance of the reduced form estimates in providing useful interpretation that can be used for inferential analysis.

The VAR model considers all variables to be jointly endogenous. This means that in a VAR, each variable is a linear function of its own and other variables' past lags, which can help capture complex dynamic properties in the data (Brooks, 2002).

The VAR model is specified as

(2)

$$y_t = \alpha + \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j y_{t-j} + u_t$$

Where $y_t = [\Delta REI_t \ \Delta INO_t \ \Delta NGR_t \ \Delta RGDP_t \ \Delta RIR_t]'$ is a vector of endogenous variables at time t , $\alpha = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_5)'$ is the (5x1) vector of constants, β_j is the j th (5x5) matrix of AR coefficients for $j = 1, \dots, p$ and $u_t = (u_{1t}, \dots, u_{5t})'$ is the (5x1) vector of error terms. The form of the unrestricted VAR model can therefore be specified as;

(3)

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta REI_t \\ \Delta INO_t \\ \Delta NGR_t \\ \Delta RGDP_t \\ \Delta RIR_t \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \\ \alpha_3 \\ \alpha_4 \\ \alpha_5 \end{bmatrix} + \beta(L) \begin{bmatrix} \Delta REI_t \\ \Delta INO_t \\ \Delta NGR_t \\ \Delta RGDP_t \\ \Delta RIR_t \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} u_{1t} \\ u_{2t} \\ u_{3t} \\ u_{4t} \\ u_{5t} \end{bmatrix}$$

where $\beta(L)$ is the polynomial lag operator. The vector of error terms is expected to be uncorrelated, with a constant variance and zero mean. In the above VAR there are n^2p free parameters. As a consequence, selecting the appropriate lag length, p , is critical. If the lag length is set too large in relation to the sample size (T), degrees of freedom will be used up, resulting in large standard errors on the estimated coefficients. Furthermore, the chosen model should have no serial correlation in the residuals.

The Granger causality test is used within this study to characterise causal relations with renewable energy investment. Granger Causality is a statistical hypothesis test which verifies whether one time series is capable of forecasting another (Granger, 1969). In order to use the Granger causality test, the data series must be stationary with zero mean.

Following this test, the dynamic response of renewable energy investment to a one standard deviation shock in all variables is analysed using the generalized impulse response functions (GIRFs) developed by Koop *et al.* (1996) and Pesaran and Shin (1998). Unlike the Cholesky identification scheme, the GIRFs do not require orthogonalization of shocks and are invariant to the ordering of endogenous variables in the VAR. Moreover, there are no identification limitations with this method.

The forecast error variance decomposition of renewable energy investment is then estimated to gain insight into the relative importance of each variable in explaining renewable energy. The variance decomposition displays the percentage of forecasting error made over time due to a specific shock. In our case, the forecast error variance decomposition is used to measure the proportion of variations in renewable energy investment caused by innovation, natural gas rent, real GDP and interest rate shocks respectively.

Finally, the historical decomposition is estimated to further evaluate sources of variation in renewable energy investment over time. Historical decomposition assigns responsibility for fluctuations in any one of the VAR's variables, among all the variables included in the model. The appropriateness of such a technique for an investigation of the drivers of renewable energy investment is transparent.

5. Data

This investigation uses annual time series data covering the time interval 1980-2020. The data consists of renewable energy investment, patent applications, natural gas rents (% of GDP), real GDP and the real interest rate which I obtained from several data sources, such as the WIPO Statistics Database, the World Bank's Database, BP Statistical Review of World Energy, the Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis and the Refinitiv Datastream. The paper uses as a dependant variable renewable energy generation (measured in terawatt-hours), which is constructed using total hydropower, solar, wind, and others. The reason for using renewable energy generation as a proxy for renewable energy investment is because the two series are highly related since the production of renewable energy is relatively costless once

installed. Moreover, I chose resident patent applications as a proxy for innovation because it is widely used in the literature and protects the intellectual property and rights of firms that seek to address environmental problems through innovation. To account for inflation, this study uses real GDP (Units: National Currency; Scale Millions) and the real interest rate which is the lending interest rate adjusted by the GDP deflator. The variables expressed as percentages above have been left in their original form, while all other variables have been transformed into logarithmic form.

5.1. Descriptive Statistics

This section reports the descriptive statistics to provide an overall perspective of the dataset.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the whole data set.

	LnREI	LnINO	NGR	LnRGDP	RIR
1: USA					
Mean	6.00	11.88	0.29	16.31	4.47
Maximum	6.72	12.60	1.78	16.76	8.59
Minimum	5.60	10.99	0.00	15.73	1.15
Std. Dev.	0.28	0.57	0.33	0.32	2.19
2: UK					
Mean	2.62	9.78	0.15	12.69	2.00
Maximum	4.90	10.00	0.35	13.06	6.39
Minimum	1.37	9.39	0.03	12.19	-4.75
Std. Dev.	1.13	0.16	0.08	0.27	3.03
3: Norway					
Mean	4.78	6.95	1.39	13.15	4.72
Maximum	5.02	7.20	3.29	13.54	16.61
Minimum	4.43	6.54	0.17	12.61	-5.63
Std. Dev.	0.14	0.17	0.93	0.30	5.23

6. Results

6.1. Unit Root Test

First, I conducted a preliminary analysis starting with testing for a unit root in all the variables. I applied the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test to assess stationarity. For this test, the null hypothesis is that the series is non-stationary while the alternative hypothesis is that the series is stationary. The number of lags to compute the ADF test has been determined using the Akaike information criterion (AIC). I decided to test for the presence of a unit root in level with the inclusion of a constant and constant plus trend. Where both tests agreed, the order of integration was determined. In

summary, the unit root analysis does reject the null hypothesis of a unit root in each of the series either in level or first difference at the 5% level of significance. Table A1 in the appendix presents unit root test results along with corresponding critical values.

6.2. Diagnostic Test

Because this paper is only concerned with estimating the short run relationship, I do not need to test for cointegration. With all variables in first difference form, except real interest rates for Norway, the VAR models were formed. Table 2 summarises the VAR estimation and diagnostic tests. For all countries, the optimal lag is selected by the AIC which indicates 0 lags for the USA, 1 lag for the UK and 2 lags for Norway. Next, I tested for serial correlation using the LM test. For this test, the null hypothesis is that there is no serial correlation at lag h while the alternative hypothesis is that there is serial correlation at lag h . Since the optimal lag selected by the AIC was 0 for USA, I decided to estimate the VAR model using 1 lag, however, this presented serial correlation at lag 1. Therefore, I estimated the VAR model using 2 lags which presented no serial correlation at lag 2. Table 2 shows the results of the LM test for serial correlation which does not reject the null hypothesis in any of the models at their respective lags. Moreover, each VAR model satisfies the stability condition since no root lies outside the unit circle. Additionally, the results of the Jarque-Bera test provide evidence of normality in the residual for the USA and Norway. Given the above results, I am able to estimate each VAR model with 1 lag for the UK and 2 lags for the USA and Norway.

Table 2. Summary of the VAR estimations and diagnostic tests.

Country	N	VAR-lag	Root	LM Test P-value	Jarque Bera, p-values					
					REI	INO	NGR	RGDP	RIR	All
USA	40	2	0.685	0.728	0.629	0.843	0.425	0.382	0.470	0.779
UK	40	1	0.592	0.075	0.508	0.837	0.231	0	0.004	0
Norway	40	2	0.778	0.226	0.855	0.751	0.811	0.438	0.841	0.973

Note: Table contains p-values for the Jarque-Bera and LM tests. The p-value represents levels of the marginal significance relating to a statistical hypothesis test, measuring the probability of an event occurring.

6.3. Granger Causality Test

First, I have applied the Granger causality test to identify which variables share causality with renewable energy investment. For the USA, the results indicate that renewable energy is driven by past movements in real GDP and real interest rates, however, innovation and natural gas rents do not Granger-cause renewable energy investment at the 5% level of significance (Appendix Table A2). Although, the null hypothesis of Granger non-causality is rejected between natural gas rents and renewable energy at the 10% level of significance. These results partially support Shah *et al.* (2018) who found a causal relationship between renewable energy and GDP, although in that study there is no evidence of causality between interest rates and renewable energy in the USA. For the UK, none of the variables have a Granger causal impact on renewable energy investment. Finally, for Norway, innovation and natural gas rents Granger-cause renewable energy investment. This suggest that these factors are relevant in driving investment into renewable energy, supporting my initial hypothesis. This finding is also consistent with the findings of Irandoust (2016), who discovered unidirectional causality from technological innovation to renewable energy in Norway. Moreover, innovation, natural gas rents, real GDP and the real interest rate jointly impact renewable energy investment in the USA and Norway, reinforcing the notion that these are relevant factors shaping the renewable energy industry.

6.4. Generalised Impulse Response Functions

After studying causality between the variables, I now evaluate the GIRFs. To assess the significance of each impulse response, the dashed lines represent a one standard error 95% confidence interval around the estimated coefficients.

First, I analysed the effects of an innovation shock and its impact on renewable energy. The GIRFs for this shock is represented in Figure 2. The shock to innovation has an insignificant effect on renewable energy in the USA and UK. This result is consistent with the Granger causality test. Furthermore, the response of renewable energy following an innovation shock is largely insignificant in Norway, except in period 3 where renewable energy investment falls by approximately 3% before gradually reaching its steady state. Recall the study by Khezri *et al.* (2021) that shows technological growth decreases the production of traditional renewable energy resources such as hydropower. This explains why renewable energy investment reacts

negatively to an innovation shock in Norway, since hydropower covers 92% of electricity generation (IEA, 2022).

Fig. 2. Renewable energy response to innovation shock.

Following this, I analysed the effects of a shock to natural gas rents on renewable energy. The GIRFs for this shock is represented in Figure 3. The shock to natural gas rents has an insignificant effect on renewable energy in the USA and UK. This is likely due to the fact that natural gas rents as a percentage of GDP are low in these countries. Finally, in Norway, the impact of a shock to natural gas rents varies in the short and long run. In period 2, renewable energy investment decreases by roughly 3% in response to a one standard deviation shock. From this I can conclude high natural gas profits encourage rent-seeking incentives and impede investments in renewable energy in the short run. However, in periods 4 and 5, renewable energy investment reacts positively, highlighting the country’s desire to accelerate renewable energy development in the long run.

Fig. 3. Renewable energy response to natural gas rent shock.

Output shocks have a delayed negative effect on renewable energy in the USA as reported in Figure 4. Following a shock to real GDP, renewable energy investment falls by a significant 4% after 3 lags before converging towards its steady state value. In general, over the time series studied, the USA has been more focused on economic growth over environmental sustainability. However, in recent years the USA has devoted its attention to addressing environmental concerns and therefore in the future I would expect this effect to reverse. Whereas, in the UK, output shocks have an insignificant effect on renewable energy investment. Furthermore, in Norway,

renewable energy investment initially falls by about 3% following a real GDP shock. However, in period 2, renewable energy investment rises by 4%, highlighting the importance of economic growth in driving renewable energy development. This parallels the findings of Alam and Murad (2020) who determine that economic growth affects renewable energy in a positive and significant manner.

Fig. 4. Renewable energy response to output shock.

Finally, monetary shocks have an insignificant effect on renewable energy in all countries. The finding is consistent with Shah *et al.* (2018) and Razmi *et al.* (2021), who find that renewable energy has a negligible response to an interest rate shock.

Fig. 5. Renewable energy response to monetary shock.

For robustness, I also computed Cholesky one standard deviation impulse responses which provided similar results to the generalised impulse responses depicted above.

6.5. Forecast Error Variance Decomposition

The forecast error variance of renewable energy is now decomposed into the contributions of all variables in the VAR model. For all countries evaluated, it is renewable energy that explains most of the variance in itself.

In relation to technology progress, the results are in line with the GIRFs, as innovation only explains a small amount of the variability of renewable energy investment, with the exception of Norway. As reported in Appendix Table A3, 13% of the variation in renewable energy is explained by innovation after 12 time periods in Norway. This is most likely due to Norway's significant expertise in the energy sector, which is being

leveraged to support innovation. Furthermore, this result parallels the findings of Alam and Murad (2020) who contribute that technological progress significantly influences renewable energy use in the Norwegian economy. Whereas in the USA and UK, approximately 2% and 3% of the variation in renewable energy can be attributed to innovation, as represented in Appendix Table A4 and A5.

Natural gas rent shocks account for roughly 3%, 0.8% and 13% of the variability in renewable energy in the USA, UK and Norway respectively. This is most likely because the USA and UK rely less on natural gas as a source of income than Norway. Furthermore, Norway has harnessed its natural gas revenues to advance modern energy systems founded on renewable energy.

Moreover, output and monetary shocks capture a significant proportion of the variation in renewable energy in the USA, 22% and 20% respectively. This suggests the nature of the renewable energy market in the USA is far more sensitive to the macroeconomy. Conversely, a small amount of the variation in renewable energy can be explained by productivity and monetary shocks in the UK, 3% and 4% respectively, which is consistent with the impulse response functions described above. Finally, the results from the variance decomposition suggest that real GDP has weak influence over renewable energy investment in Norway, contrary to the impulse response. Likewise, real interest rates are strongly exogenous. This indicates that macroeconomic factors are less relevant within the market for renewable energy in Norway, with technology progress and earnings from natural gas playing a more important role.

These results reflect the different nature of the renewable energy market in the USA, UK and Norway. For instance, the USA has a relatively deregulated energy market over the time series studied, with fewer policies encouraging renewable energy through tax and subsidy systems. As a result, the renewable energy industry is far more market oriented compared to the UK and Norway. Although the UK has a relatively competitive renewable energy market, policies such as the Renewable Obligation and the Contracts for Difference scheme have increased government intervention in the renewable sector, making it less market oriented than the USA. In contrast, the Norwegian government plays a less active role in promoting renewable energy, falling between these two extremes. This is due to its sophisticated hydro-electric industry

which operates in a market environment and therefore doesn't require high levels of subsidies for hydropower development, as illustrated by Shah *et al.* (2018).

6.6. Historical Decomposition

The historical fluctuations of renewable energy investment are now examined through the lenses of innovation, natural gas rent, real GDP, and interest rate shocks. The blue bar reflects the total effect of all stochastic components, which can be compared to the effect from the specified stochastic component.

In the USA, the historical decomposition of renewable energy can be explained by innovation between 1990-2000 as represented in Figure 6. During this period, the USA witnessed significant advancements in environmental technologies especially following the Energy Policy Act (EPAAct) which was signed into law in 1992 (IEA, 2019a). EPAAct 1992 motivated the development of renewable sources through tax incentives which explains why we observe this volatility. Thereafter, the impact of innovation is insignificant. Furthermore, the historical decomposition of renewable energy in Norway can be attributed to innovation particularly beyond 2010 where technology progress has played a critical role in paving the way for a more sustainable future in Norway. In contrast, innovation explains a small amount of the historical variability in renewable energy in the UK which is in line with the results from the variance decomposition.

Fig. 6. Historical decomposition of renewable energy to innovation shocks

As highlighted in Figure 7, natural gas rent is responsible for an inconsiderable amount of the historical variability in renewable energy investment in the USA across the time series recorded. This complements the results from the variance decomposition. On the other hand, between 2000-2005, natural gas rents explained a significant amount of the historical variance in renewable energy in the UK. In the early 2000s, natural gas rents were subject to domestic production declines, leading

to a rapid increase in gas imports, which explains the notable variation in renewable energy investment. In recent years, however, imports have stabilised due to the maximised recovery of domestic gas (IEA, 2019b). Moreover, renewable energy has witnessed material variation driven by natural gas rents over the last 15 years in Norway. Natural gas rent volatility was prevalent during this time period as a result of increased carbon taxes to decarbonise the industry sector (IEA, 2022).

Fig. 7. Historical decomposition of renewable energy to natural gas rent shocks

In the USA, the historical decomposition of renewable energy can be explained by real GDP throughout the time series recorded as depicted in Figure 8. This is consistent with the findings of the variance decomposition, which demonstrates the vital role of economic growth in determining renewable energy investment. Whereas, in the UK real GDP is insignificant in explaining the historical decomposition of renewable energy. Finally, in contrast to the results from the variance decomposition, real GDP is an important driver of the historical variability in renewable energy investment in Norway, particularly beyond 2010. During this period the Norwegian government has been working to create a more market-oriented environment in response to growing international demand for renewable energy.

Fig. 8. Historical decomposition of renewable energy to output shocks

Lastly, the historical variability of renewable energy investment is largely driven by monetary shocks in the USA, especially during the 1990s which were characterised by a period of volatility in interest rates as the economy entered an early recession. Likewise, real interest rate shocks are responsible for a considerable amount of the historical variability in renewable energy investment in the UK also during the 1990s.

This era was marked by high inflation, which resulted in prolonged periods of high interest rates (Bank of England Database, 2023). In contrast, the real interest rate is insignificant in Norway as shown in Figure 9. This is most likely due to the fact that interest rates in Norway have remained relatively stable over the time series studied.

Fig. 9. Historical decomposition of renewable energy to monetary shocks

In summary, the results of the historical variance decomposition are very interesting, specifically in relation to the Paris Agreement adopted in 2015. In the UK, the interaction between renewable energy investment and its related variables are significantly affected following the Paris Agreement. In contrast, there is no significant effect in the USA. The USA formally withdrew from the Paris Agreement in 2020 after President Trump announced the move in June 2017, suggesting that it was never taken seriously. Moreover, the impact of the Paris Agreement in Norway is negligible because the country did not need to take much action due to its already dominant position in the fight against climate change.

6.7. Robustness Check

I further do some robustness checks by replacing natural gas rents with natural resource rents in Eq. (3). Natural resource rents comprise the sum of oil, natural gas, and coal rents, and are thus a reliable metric for evaluating the baseline results. With a few exceptions, I find that the empirical results are nearly identical to the corresponding baseline results with natural resource rents. The results from this check are reported in the Appendix.

7. Discussion

7.1. Policy Implications

First, this study has conveyed the importance of innovation in the context of renewable energy. The discussion about technological innovation and renewable energy is beneficial because each country has advanced technology capabilities and is currently pursuing ambitious energy transition goals. The overall results reveal that technological innovation is a decisive factor of renewable energy investment in Norway. This is most likely due to its impressive R&D spending as a share of GDP on energy-related technologies. Therefore, the USA and UK should prioritise investment in the development of renewable energy over investment in existing infrastructure in order to foster an innovative culture dedicated to advancing energy technologies. However, an effective carbon pricing strategy is also required to encourage innovation in renewable energy.

Second, this paper offers the first empirical investigation of the effect of natural gas rents on renewable energy investment. This is especially important given the recent volatility in natural gas markets. The study shows that while overall natural gas abundance may be conducive, natural gas rents negatively affect renewable energy investment in Norway in the short run. This indicates that countries still struggle to resist rent-seeking incentives even in the presence of powerful democratic institutions. Thus, countries with abundant natural gas reserves should establish renewable energy financing facilities in order to utilise natural gas rents. Moreover, in line with Ahmadov and van der Borg (2019), stronger regulatory interventions are required to tackle the pernicious effects of natural gas. In contrast, countries with low natural gas reserves are not required to take any action due to the negligible impact of natural gas rents on renewable energy.

Furthermore, this study raises a number of significant macroeconomic policy implications for energy policies. As previously stated, evidence suggests that renewable energy markets differ fundamentally across countries, depending on government renewable energy policy. Where a country's energy sector is more market-oriented, as in the USA, the renewable energy industry has a strong relationship with macroeconomic factors. Renewable energy, on the other hand, will be less sensitive to changes in macroeconomic aggregates in countries such as the UK, where the energy sector receives significant government support. Given the recent volatility in economic activity as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic, it is critical to design policies that take

into account the need to smooth renewable energy investment throughout the business life cycle. In the USA, for example, in response to a positive output shock, policymakers should increase fiscal incentives, such as renewable energy subsidies or fossil fuel taxation, to mitigate the negative impact on renewable energy investment. Whereas, in Norway, policymakers have the opportunity to reduce fiscal incentives in response to a positive output shock.

7.2. Future Research and Limitations

For future research, this paper further opens up the scope for additional investigation into the determinants of renewable energy investment which may be beneficial in understanding its deeper regulatory, economic and environmental causes. Furthermore, evaluating the relationship between renewable energy investment and natural gas rents in gas-rich countries with weak institutional frameworks may be interesting to extend the literature within this area. Another study could evaluate the historical decomposition of renewable energy in the USA following President Biden's executive order to rejoin the Paris Agreement. Additionally, empirical studies on the effect of different proxies for renewable energy investment and innovation would increase the robustness of the result. Moreover, as is customary with this type of study, a longer time series would have been beneficial.

8. Conclusion

This paper has studied the interrelationship between renewable energy investment, innovation, natural gas rents and macroeconomic factors in the USA, UK and Norway during the period 1980-2020 by constructing a VAR model. The countries evaluated within this study are three of the most significant and influential nations in the context of renewable energy development.

The reality or lack of a causal relationship between the variables, as determined by the Granger causality test, implies some differences between the underlying economies. The study discovered all of the variables cause renewable energy investment, with the exception of the UK. This causal relationship shed light on some crucial channels through which innovation, natural gas rents and macroeconomic factors can affect the deployment of renewable energy in the USA and Norway.

In addition, the findings of the GIRFs have important implications. The results illustrate both the negative and positive effects of natural gas rent on renewable energy investment in Norway. Moreover, the findings also indicate that real GDP shocks have a moderately negative and statistically significant effect on renewable energy investment in the USA, most likely because the country prioritised economic growth over environmental issues during the time series studied. Whereas, in Norway the effect is mostly positive due to the country's sophisticated renewable technical infrastructure.

The forecast error variance decomposition results reflect the distinct nature of the renewable energy markets in all three countries studied. In the USA, renewable energy investment is driven by past movements in real GDP and interest rates, due to its market orientated approach. However, because of extensive government support, the variables in the UK are insignificant in explaining the variation in renewable energy investment, making it less susceptible to economic factors. Finally, innovation and natural gas rents explained a significant proportion of the variance in renewable energy investment in Norway due to harnessing energy-related technologies and natural gas revenues.

Finally, the results from the historical decomposition highlight the importance of all variables in driving renewable energy investment. Consistent with the forecast error variance decomposition, the historical fluctuations of renewable energy investment are sensitive to real GDP and interest rate shocks in the USA. In Norway, the historical variance of renewable energy is influenced by its related variables across multiple subsamples, with the exception of interest rates. This implies that renewable energy investment in Norway is less sensitive to borrowing costs. Finally, only in the UK did the Paris Agreement's climate change commitment have a significant impact on the interaction between renewable energy investment and its related variables, indicating that the country took the agreement very seriously, especially compared to the USA.

Overall, the study's remarkable conclusion is that innovation, natural gas rents, and macroeconomic factors all play an important role in determining renewable energy investment, which varies substantially across countries.

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10. Appendix A

Note Tables A1-A5 relate to the baseline results. Figures A1-A8 and Tables A6-9 relate to the robustness model with natural resource rents.

Fig. A1. Robust renewable energy response to innovation shock.

Fig. A2. Robust renewable energy response to natural resource rent shock.

Fig. A3. Robust renewable energy response to output shock.

Fig. A4. Robust renewable energy response to monetary shock.

Fig. A5. Historical decomposition of renewable energy to innovation shocks

Fig. A6. Historical decomposition of renewable energy to natural resource rent shocks

Fig. A7. Historical decomposition of renewable energy to output shocks

Fig. A8. Historical decomposition of renewable energy to monetary shocks

Table A1. Unit root test results.

		ADF	
Variables		Constant	Constant plus Trend
USA			
Renewable Energy	Level	0.4	-1.19
	1st difference	-6.33*	-6.4*
Patent Applications	Level	-1.09	-0.49
	1st difference	-5.68*	-5.8*
Natural Gas Rents	Level	-1.59	-2.36
	1st difference	-3.04*	-7.76*
Real GDP	Level	-2.06	-1.27
	1st difference	-6.37*	-6.5*
Real Interest Rates	Level	-1.9	-1.93
	1st difference	-5.94*	-4*
UK			
Renewable Energy	Level	3.03*	-1.22
	1st difference	-7.41*	-9.45*
Patent Applications	Level	-0.02	-1.26
	1st difference	-4.28*	-4.34*
Natural Gas Rents	Level	-2.93	-2.91
	1st difference	-6.15*	-4.85*
Real GDP	Level	-1.02	-2.03
	1st difference	-4*	-4.05*
Real Interest Rates	Level	-2.77	-2.76
	1st difference	-8.06*	-7.97*
Norway			
Renewable Energy	Level	-1.38	-4.71*
	1st difference	-4.73*	-4.75*
Patent Applications	Level	-2.31	-1.24
	1st difference	-3.62*	-6.84*
Natural Gas Rents	Level	-1.69	-2.84
	1st difference	-6.41*	-6.23*
Real GDP	Level	-1.7	-1.25
	1st difference	-3.95*	-4.23*
Real Interest Rates	Level	-3.62*	-4.39*
	1st difference	-5.71*	-5.85*
Critical values			
Model with constant		Model with constant plus trend	
1%	-3.605593	1%	-4.205004

5%	-2.936942	5%	-3.526609
10%	-2.606857	10%	-3.194611

Note: * Indicate the level of significance at the 5%.

Table A2. Granger causality/block exogeneity Wald tests.

Null Hypothesis	Chi-square	lag	Prob.
1: USA			
Δ INO does not Granger cause Δ REI	0.60	2	0.74
Δ NGR does not Granger cause Δ REI	5.46	2	0.07
Δ RGDP does not Granger cause Δ REI	17.99	2	0.00
Δ RIR does not Granger cause Δ REI	12.33	2	0.00
All Δ INO, Δ NGR, Δ RGDP and Δ RIR does not Granger cause Δ REI	22.27	2	0.00
2: UK			
Δ INO does not Granger cause Δ REI	0.92	1	0.34
Δ NGR does not Granger cause Δ REI	0.26	1	0.61
Δ RGDP does not Granger cause Δ REI	0.02	1	0.89
Δ RIR does not Granger cause Δ REI	1.95	1	0.16
All Δ INO, Δ NGR, Δ RGDP and Δ RIR does not Granger cause Δ REI	3.19	1	0.53
3: Norway			
Δ INO does not Granger cause Δ REI	6.91	2	0.03
Δ NGR does not Granger cause Δ REI	14.79	2	0.00
Δ RGDP does not Granger cause Δ REI	3.27	2	0.20
Δ RIR does not Granger cause Δ REI	3.96	2	0.14
All Δ INO, Δ NGR, Δ RGDP and Δ RIR does not Granger cause Δ REI	22.64	2	0.00

Table A3. Forecast error variance decompositions of renewable energy USA.

Period	Renewable	Innovation	Gas Rent	Output	Interest Rate
1	100.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
2	98.667	1.233	0.085	0.014	0.000
3	59.143	1.710	0.275	19.999	18.873
4	56.815	1.579	2.443	20.277	18.886
5	55.879	2.009	2.503	20.012	19.597
6	54.287	1.977	2.432	21.250	20.054
7	54.025	1.965	2.524	21.506	19.980
8	53.908	1.976	2.554	21.518	20.044
9	53.780	1.984	2.550	21.595	20.092
10	53.765	1.987	2.555	21.606	20.087
11	53.758	1.988	2.556	21.611	20.087
12	53.749	1.988	2.556	21.620	20.087

Table A4. Forecast error variance decompositions of renewable energy UK.

Period	Renewable	Innovation	Gas Rent	Output	Interest Rate
1	100.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
2	91.816	2.475	0.743	1.311	3.655
3	89.881	2.549	0.794	2.853	3.923
4	89.771	2.585	0.838	2.890	3.916
5	89.732	2.622	0.838	2.890	3.918
6	89.717	2.624	0.840	2.901	3.919
7	89.712	2.625	0.840	2.903	3.919
8	89.711	2.626	0.840	2.904	3.919
9	89.711	2.626	0.841	2.904	3.919
10	89.710	2.626	0.841	2.904	3.919
11	89.710	2.626	0.841	2.904	3.919
12	89.710	2.626	0.841	2.904	3.919

Table A5. Forecast error variance decompositions of renewable energy Norway.

Period	Renewable	Innovation	Gas Rent	Output	Interest Rate
1	100.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
2	83.272	2.616	7.454	6.639	0.019
3	72.578	9.677	9.622	6.304	1.819
4	69.354	10.126	11.832	6.265	2.423
5	67.241	11.034	13.234	6.112	2.379
6	66.275	11.623	13.271	6.017	2.814
7	66.290	11.654	13.221	5.995	2.840
8	65.793	12.311	13.114	5.950	2.832
9	65.654	12.466	13.116	5.936	2.829
10	65.574	12.524	13.142	5.927	2.833
11	65.566	12.534	13.133	5.926	2.842
12	65.573	12.532	13.126	5.926	2.843

Table A6. Robust Granger causality/block exogeneity Wald tests.

Null Hypothesis	Chi-square	lag	Prob.
1: USA			
Δ INO does not Granger cause Δ REI	1.27	2	0.53
Δ NRR does not Granger cause Δ REI	4.68	2	0.10
Δ RGDP does not Granger cause Δ REI	16.53	2	0.00
Δ RIR does not Granger cause Δ REI	11.45	2	0.00
All Δ INO, Δ NRR, Δ RGDP and Δ RIR does not Granger cause Δ REI	21.07	2	0.01
2: UK			
Δ INO does not Granger cause Δ REI	0.64	1	0.42
Δ NRR does not Granger cause Δ REI	0.12	1	0.73
Δ RGDP does not Granger cause Δ REI	0.00	1	0.96

ΔRIR does not Granger cause ΔREI	2.03	1	0.15
All ΔINO , ΔNRR , $\Delta RGDP$ and ΔRIR does not Granger cause ΔREI	3.03	1	0.55

3: Norway

ΔINO does not Granger cause ΔREI	3.25	2	0.20
ΔNRR does not Granger cause ΔREI	3.11	2	0.21
$\Delta RGDP$ does not Granger cause ΔREI	2.77	2	0.25
ΔRIR does not Granger cause ΔREI	1.33	2	0.52
All ΔINO , ΔNRR , $\Delta RGDP$ and ΔRIR does not Granger cause ΔREI	8.76	2	0.36

Table A7. Robust forecast error variance decompositions of renewable energy USA.

Period	Renewable	Innovation	Natural Resource Rent	Output	Interest Rate
1	100.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
2	98.073	1.393	0.139	0.171	0.224
3	66.980	2.152	0.122	11.581	19.165
4	63.996	2.124	2.981	11.218	19.680
5	63.036	2.374	3.322	11.239	20.029
6	61.291	2.356	3.228	12.936	20.188
7	60.779	2.352	3.444	13.326	20.099
8	60.591	2.353	3.605	13.317	20.134
9	60.413	2.384	3.604	13.421	20.177
10	60.367	2.397	3.624	13.451	20.162
11	60.351	2.398	3.633	13.466	20.152
12	60.332	2.401	3.634	13.484	20.149

Table A8. Robust forecast error variance decompositions of renewable energy UK.

Period	Renewable	Innovation	Natural Resource Rent	Output	Interest Rate
1	100.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
2	92.238	2.486	0.512	1.036	3.728
3	90.682	2.549	0.559	2.070	4.140
4	90.650	2.576	0.563	2.079	4.132
5	90.619	2.604	0.563	2.081	4.133
6	90.606	2.606	0.563	2.091	4.134
7	90.602	2.608	0.563	2.094	4.134
8	90.600	2.609	0.563	2.094	4.134
9	90.599	2.609	0.563	2.095	4.134
10	90.599	2.609	0.563	2.095	4.134
11	90.598	2.609	0.563	2.095	4.134
12	90.598	2.609	0.563	2.095	4.134

Table A9. Robust forecast error variance decompositions of renewable energy Norway.

Period	Renewable	Innovation	Natural Resource Rent	Output	Interest Rate
1	100.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
2	90.576	1.889	0.043	7.490	0.002

3	81.583	6.309	2.521	7.576	2.011
4	78.672	6.556	4.743	7.838	2.191
5	78.272	6.504	4.928	7.750	2.546
6	77.829	6.399	5.537	7.692	2.542
7	77.873	6.356	5.556	7.685	2.530
8	77.694	6.376	5.569	7.712	2.649
9	77.665	6.395	5.586	7.707	2.647
10	77.639	6.393	5.598	7.714	2.657
11	77.627	6.395	5.604	7.715	2.659
12	77.614	6.393	5.622	7.713	2.658
